

No. 17—MANDHATA PLATES OF PARAMARA JAYASIMHA-JAYAVARMAN,
V. S. 1331

(4 Plates)

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In November 1939, Mr. R. B. Deshpande of Dhār, formerly Assistant Engineer of the old Dhār State in Central India and in charge of the archaeological monuments at Māṇḍlū, learnt from a Brāhmaṇa named Subrahmanya Shastri about the existence of a new copper-plate inscription in the possession of Rao Saheb Sobhag Singhji, the then Rao of Māṇdhātā. The inscription is said to have been discovered in 1927 at Māṇdhātā on the southern Bank of the Narmadā, when some people were clearing the ground near the Kāśī-Viśvāśvara temple for the Kārttikī Mēlā. Mr. Deshpande visited Māṇdhātā in the company of Shastri and succeeded in examining the inscription through the kindness and courtesy of the Rao Saheb. The plates, which were thoroughly covered with verdigris at the time of their discovery, were cleaned and Mr. Deshpande took a few sets of impressions of the writing. The inscription was then studied by Pandit Babu Shastri of Dhār and his transcript with a Hindi translation was published in the monthly journal called *Ushā*, published by the Bhōj Prakāśan, Dhār, in its issues for January-February 1953, p. 46 ; March 1953, p. 14 ; November 1953, p. 44 ; December 1953, p. 11 ; February 1954, p. 28 ; March 1954, p. 9 ; August 1954, pp. 27-28 ; and October-November 1954, pp. 41-42. Mr. Deshpande also published an introductory note in English on the importance of the inscription in the same journal in its issues for November 1953, p. 43, and December 1953, pp. 20-21.

About the beginning of 1955 I received information about the existence of the inscription and tried to secure it on loan for examination from the Rao Saheb of Māṇdhātā. But I was informed that the record was then being examined by Dr. H. V. Trivedi, Curator of the Indore Museum. Failing to secure the original plates, I then tried to secure a set of its impressions from Mr. R. B. Deshpande. This attempt was luckily successful and about the middle of the year I received one set of inked impressions of the record from Mr. Deshpande and copies of the issues of the *Ushā*, containing the articles of Pandit Babu Shastri and Mr. Deshpande, from Mr. Y. W. Wankar of Dhār, formerly Lecturer in Geography in the Government College, Dhār. The impressions were photographed in my office and returned to Mr. Deshpande. In this connection I received very considerable help from Mr. N. S. Purandare of Dhār, formerly Principal of the Government College, Mandasaur.

Since, however, the impressions received from Mr. Deshpande were not quite satisfactory, I requested Dr. Trivedi to send me either the original plates on loan or a set of good impressions of the inscription. I also requested him to publish the record in the *Epigraphia Indica*. Unfortunately nothing was received from Dr. Trivedi till the beginning of the year 1957 and I took up the photographs of Mr. Deshpande's impressions for study in April 1957. On examination it was found that the inscription throws welcome light on the history of the Paramāras of Malwa, although Pandit Babu Shastri's transcript is not free from inaccuracies and his translation is full of errors while Mr. Deshpande's views on the importance and interpretation of the record are all misconceived. The inscription is edited here from the photographs referred to above.

The set consists of **four** plates, each measuring about 17 inches in length, 13 inches in height and between $\frac{1}{8}$ and $\frac{3}{16}$ inch in thickness. Their weight has not been recorded. The edges of the plates were raised to the thickness of about $\frac{1}{4}$ inch for the protection of the writing. The

four plates are held together by two copper rings passing through holes made in them. While the first plate has writing only on the inner side, the other three plates bear inscription on both obverse and reverse. In the left side of the empty space beneath the writing on the reverse of the last plate, the figure of **Garuḍa**, the royal emblem of the Paramāras, is engraved as in so many other Paramāra charters.¹ There are altogether 140 lines of writing in the inscription and they are distributed on the inscribed faces of the plates in the following order : I—21 lines : IIA—22 lines ; IIB—23 lines : IIIA—23 lines ; IIIB—23 lines ; IVA—23 lines ; IVB—5 lines.

The **characters** of the inscription are Nāgarī. Its **language** is Sanskrit. The record is written in a mixture of prose and verse. Its **palaeography** and **orthography** do not call for any special remark. The letter *b* is indicated by the sign for *v*. There is a general tendency to represent class nasals by *anusvāra*. Final *m* is often wrongly changed to *anusvāra* at the end of the second and fourth feet of verses, although it is generally used correctly at the end of sentences in the prose part of the document. The **date** of the charter is quoted in words in lines 91-92 as Friday, Maitra(Anurādhā)-nakshatra, Bhādrapada-sudi 7 in the year (Vikrama Saṃvat) 1331 called **Pramāthin** (according to the Northern Cycle of Jupiter). The details of the date correspond regularly to those of the **10th of August in the year 1274 A. D.**

The **object** of the document is to record a grant of land made by *Sāulhanika* **Anayasimhadēva** while he was staying at Maṇḍapa-durga, with the permission of the **Paramāra** king **Jayavarman** *alias* **Jayasimha**, described as the lord of **Dhārā**, after having worshipped the husband of Pārvatī, i.e. the god Śiva. Anayasimha's order in this respect was addressed to the officials as well as the villagers including Brāhmaṇas and Paṭṭakilas (i.e. Patels) who were associated with the following localities : (1) Kumbhaḍāuda-grāma in Vardhanāpura-pratijāgaraṇaka, (2) Vālauda-grāma in the same *Pratijāgaraṇaka* (i.e. Pargana), (3) Vaghāḷī-grāma in Saptāśīti-pratijāgaraṇaka and (4) Nāṭiyā-grāma in Nāgadaha-pratijāgaraṇaka. It is stated that Anayasimha, together with his four sons named Kamalasiṃha, Dhārasimha, Jaitrasimha and Padmasimha, granted the said four villages in favour of a number of Brāhmaṇas residing in the Brahmapurī (i.e. Brāhmaṇa settlement) at Māndhātṛi and belonging to various *gōtras* and *śākhās*, whose families hailed from several localities. It is interesting to note that the four villages were divided into 16 parts, each called a *pada* and that, while 14 of these *padas* were granted to the 14 Brāhmaṇa donees, 2 *padas* were made over by Anayasimha to his own self. It may be that Anayasimha purchased the four villages from the Paramāra king for the purpose of creating a rent-free holding to be granted in favour of Brāhmaṇas, although he was allowed to retain a small part of the land for himself. There are other instances of this kind in inscriptions.²

The donees mentioned in the list are the following : (1) Dī(Dīkshita) Padmanābhaśarman, son of Avasathin Vidyādharasārman and grandson of Cha(Chaturvēdin) Kamalādharasārman of the Gautama *gōtra*, the Āṅgīrasa, Auvathya and Gautama *pravaras* and the Ṛigvēda *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī ; (2) Cha(Chaturvēdin) Mādhabasārman, brother of No. 1 ; (3) Paṃ(Paṇḍita) Śrikanṭhasārman, son of Pañchapī(pā)ṭhin Miśra Uddharasārman and grandson of Miśra Dharmadharasārman of the Bhāradvāja *gōtra*, the Āṅgīrasa, Bārhaspatya and Bhāradvāja *pravaras* and the Ṛigvēda *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī ; (4) Dvi(Dvivēdin) Gōvardhanasārman, son of Paṃ(Paṇḍita) Vidyāpatīśarman and grandson of Cha(Chaturvēdin) Bhūpatīśarman of the Kāśyapa *gōtra*, the Kāśyapa, Āvatsara and Naidhruva *pravaras* and the Ṛigvēda *śākhā* and

¹ Cf. above, Vol. IX, Plate facing p. 111.

² See *IHQ*, Vol. XXIII, p. 236. The Baud plates of Prithvīmahādēvī appear to offer another instance (cf. above, Vol. XXIX, p. 211 and note 1) ; but the expression *dāna-patī* (i.e. the person creating a rent-free holding with the approval of the royal authority) has been misunderstood by the editor of the inscriptions.

hailing from Lakhanapura : (5) Dī(Dīkshita) Vāmanaśarman, son of Dī° Dēvaśarman and grandson of Dī° Śrīvatsaśarman of the Chandrātrēya *gōtra*, the Ātrēya, Gāvishthira and Pūrvātitha *pravaras* and the Mādhyandina *śākhā* and hailing from Tōlāpauha : (6) Avasthī (Avasathin) Anantaśarman, son of Sādhāraṇaśarman and grandson of Balabhadraśarman of the Vāsishthā *gōtra*, the Vāsishthā, Śāktrya and Pārāśarya *pravaras* and the Mādhyandina *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī : (7) Dvi(Dvivēdin) Hariśarmaśarman, son of Dvi° Sōlūśarman and grandson of Śukla Pradyumnaśarman of the Bhāradvāja *gōtra*, the Āngirasa, Bārhaspatya and Bhāradvāja *pravaras* and the Mādhyandina *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī ; (8) Dvi(Dvivēdin) Mahādēvaśarman, son of Upā(Upādhyāya) Vaijūśarman and grandson of Upā° Dēvaśarman of the Kāśyapa *gōtra*, the Kāśyapa, Āvatsāra and Naidhruva *pravaras* and the Mādhyandina *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭēnī : (9) Dvi(Dvivēdin) Haridēvaśarman, son of Ava(Avasathin) Āladēvaśarman and grandson of Pā(Pāṭhin) Kūlhaṇaśarman of the Kātyāyana *gōtra*, the Viśvāmitra, Kātya and Kīla(Atkīla) *pravaras* and the Mādhyandina *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī ; (10) Dvi(Dvivēdin) Anantaśarman, son of Ava(Avasathin) Vīnkūdēvaśarman and grandson of Dvi° Gajādharāśarman of the Bhāradvāja *gōtra*, the Āngirasa, Bārhaspatya and Bhāradvāja *pravaras* and the Mādhyandina *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī ; (11) Pā(Pāṭhin) Yōgēśvaraśarman, son of Pā° Atriśarman and grandson of Pā° Kṛishṇaśarman of the Ātrēya *gōtra*, the Ātrēya, Gāvishthira and Pūrvātitha *pravaras* and the Mādhyandina *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī : (12) Tri(Trivēdin) Nārāyaṇaśarman, son of Tri° Dāmōdaraśarman and grandson of Tri° Samuddharaṇaśarman of the Vāsishthā *gōtra*, the Vāsishthā, Abharadvasu and Indrapramada *pravaras* and the Kauthuma *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī ; (13) Tri(Trivēdin) Purushūśarman, son of Cha(Chaturvēdin) Lakshmīdharaśarman and grandson of Cha° Vāsudēvaśarman of the Sāvārṇi *gōtra*, the Bhārgava, Chyavana, Āpnavad, Aurva and Jāmadagnya *pravaras* and the Kauthuma *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī ; (14) Tri(Trivēdin) Vāūśarman, son of Tri° Mahēśvaraśarman and grandson of Tri° Viśvēśvaraśarman of the Śāṇḍilya *gōtra*, the Śāṇḍilya, Āsita and Daivala *pravaras* and the Kauthuma *śākhā* and hailing from Ṭakārī : and (15) Sādhanika Anayasimhavarman of the Chāhamāna family and Kshatriya community, son of Sā° Salakhaṇasimhavarman and grandson of Sā° Palhaṇadēvavarman of the Vatsa *gōtra* and the Bhārgava, Chyavana, Āpnavad, Aurva and Jāmadagnya *pravaras*.

An interesting feature of the list of the donees quoted above is that, in several of the cases, the family names were not still stereotyped in the families since the donee and his father and grandfather have not the same distinctive designation. In one case, Avasathin Vidyādharāśarman is stated to have been the son of Chaturvēdin Kamalādharāśarman and the father of Dīkshita Padmanābhaśarman and Chaturvēdin Mādhaśarman. The mention of the *gōtra* of the Kshatriya family of the Chāhamānas is also worth noting. But more interesting seems to be the fact that, while the list enumerates only 14 Brāhmaṇas getting one *pada* or share each, along with the Chāhamāna Kshatriya Anayasimha receiving two *padas*, line 127 specifically gives the number of donees as '16 Brāhmaṇas'. It is therefore not impossible that the 16 shares in which the 4 gift villages were divided had been originally planned to be allotted to 16 Brāhmaṇas but that the plan was later modified to the advantage of Anayasimha. Whether this was done with the king's consent or by Anayasimha on his own initiative without his master's knowledge cannot be determined, although the mention of the 15 donees including himself as '16 Brāhmaṇas' looks rather suspicious. Line 133 also refers to the donees of the grant as 'these Brāhmaṇas'.

The fact that Anayasimha is stated to have granted the charter, albeit with the king's permission, points to his power and prestige in the court of the Paramāra king. He is stated to have been staying at Maṇḍapa-durga and is called a *Sādhanika*. His immediate ancestors also appear to have enjoyed the same designation. The expression *Sādhanika* is the same as Prakrit *Sāhaṇia*

meaning 'the commander of an army'.¹ An inscription (V. S. 1237)² of a Paramāra chief named Jaḍaṇa, from Nāṇa in the old Jodhpur State, uses the same word as *Sāhaṇi* (cf. the family name Sāhni) which has been supposed to indicate 'the master of the royal stables'. In Mērutuṅga's *Prabandhachintāmaṇi* the expression *Mahāsādhānika* is used in the sense of a chieftain or military governor.³

We have seen that the list of donees discussed above mentions Sā° Salakhaṇasiṃhavarman and Sā° Palhaṇadēvavarman respectively as the father and grandfather of Chāhamāna Anayasimha. Verses 57-66 (lines 75-86) of the introductory part of the inscription offer further information about this Chāhamāna family owing allegiance to the Paramāras. Verses 75-76 speak of *Rāntta* (i.e. *Rāvat* from Sanskrit *Rāja-putra*) Rāṭa and his son Palhaṇadēva (respectively the great-grandfather and grandfather of Anayasimha) and of the power of their arms. The master of Palhaṇadēva is vaguely referred to without disclosing his name, although he must have been the contemporary Paramāra king. Verse 59 mentions Palhaṇadēva's son Salakhaṇasiṃha who is stated to have assisted **Arjunadēva** in his battles. This Arjunadēva is no doubt the Paramāra king Arjunavarman whose known dates are V. S. 1267 (1211 A. D.), 1270 (1213 A. D.) and 1272 (1215 A. D.).⁴ It is not impossible that the said Chāhamāna chief is identical with *Rājan* Salakhaṇa mentioned as the *Mahāsāndhi* (i.e. *Mahāsāndhivigrahika*) in Arjunavarman's Bhopal plates (Set 2).⁵ A very interesting instance of military assistance rendered by Salakhaṇasiṃha to the Paramāra king is offered by verse 60. It is stated that the Chāhamāna leader of Paramāra forces defeated the army of **Simhaṇadēva**, no doubt the Yādava king of that name who ruled in c. 1210-47 A. D., and captured seven plumes (*chāmarāṇi* which appear to have been fitted with the turban) from the general Sāgaya-rāṇaka, apparently a leader of Simhaṇadēva's forces, after having pulled the general down from his horse which was in the middle of a contingent. This feat of valour pleased both Simha and Arjuna (i.e. Paramāra Arjunavarman) who shook their heads in appreciation.

The Bahal inscription⁶ of Yādava Simhaṇa and the Paithan plates⁷ of his great-grandson Rāmachandra (c. 1271-1310 A. D.) refer to Simhaṇa's victory over Arjuna who is none other than the Paramāra king Arjunavarman of Malwa. The *Hammīramadāmadana* relates how Chāhamāna Sindhurāja, brother of Arjunavarman's feudatory Simha of Lāṭadēśa, was killed by Yādava Simhaṇa.⁸ This Simha of Lāṭa seems to be mentioned as appreciating the valour of Chāhamāna Salakhaṇa in verse 60 of our inscription, referred to above. The stanza, therefore, probably refers to the Yādava invasion of Lāṭa which formed a part of the dominions of Arjunavarman. Sāgaya-rāṇaka, who was a leader of the Yādava army and was defeated by the Chāhamāna general of the Paramāra king, may be the same as the cavalry officer Saṅga mentioned in a Yādava inscription⁹ of Śaka 1119 (1197 A. D.).

¹ H. T. Seth, *Pāiasaddamahānava*, s.v.

² Bhandarkar's List, No. 395.

³ Cf. Ganguly, *History of the Paramāras of Malwa*, p. 212. *Mahāsādhānika* seems to be the same as *Paṭṭasāhaṇādhipati* of some records (cf. *A.R. Ep.*, 1953-54, p. 6). For *Sāhaṇi* or *Sāhni* in other inscriptions, see also loc. cit.; Kundangar, *Inscriptions of Northern Karnatak and Kolhapur*, p. 139, No. 16, etc.

⁴ Bhandarkar's List, Nos. 457, 460 and 466.

⁵ *JAOS*, Vol. VII, pp. 25 ff. Salakhana mentioned in the Bhopal plates is generally identified with the homonymous father of the Jain poet Āsādhara author of the *Trishashṭismṛiti* and various other works and a protégé of Arjunavarman and his successors (cf. Ray, *Dynastic History of Northern India*, Vol. II, p. 899; Ganguly, op. cit., p. 202).

⁶ Above, Vol. III, pp. 113 ff. Cf. Hēmādri's *Vratakhanda* (*Bomb. Gaz.*, Vol. I, part ii, p. 272, verse 43).

⁷ *Ind. Ant.*, Vol. XIV, p. 316, text line 27.

⁸ Ganguly, op. cit., pp. 208, 212-13. Cf. *Hammīramadāmadana*, Anka I.

⁹ See Kundangar, op. cit., p. 146, No. 17.

The following six stanzas (verses 61-66) describe the activities of **Anayasimha**, the son of Salakhana and the donor of the grant. He is stated to have built a temple for the god Śiva and excavated a tank at Dēvapālapura. This locality seems to have been named after the Paramāra king Dēvapāla who succeeded Arjunavarman. Another temple was built by him at Śākapura for the goddess Ambikā. This locality may have been the headquarters of the Pargana called Śākapura-pratijāgarāṇaka which is mentioned in the Piplianagar plates¹ of Arjunavarman. Anayasimha also built a temple for the god Jambukēśvara Śiva in the vicinity of the Ōṅkāra (i.e. Ōṅkā-rēśvara) temple and excavated a tank near the former. In the fort of Maṇḍapa, he excavated a tank and granted in favour of Brāhmaṇas, with the king's permission, a *purī* or township having a surrounding wall, a gate, a big shrine and a pond and containing 16 temples endowed with golden jars [forming their pinnacles]. This *purī* is apparently the Brahmapurī at Maṇḍapadurga, mentioned as the habitation of the Brāhmaṇa donees of the grant under discussion and already referred to above. Similar pious works were also done by Anayasimha at Māndhātṛi-durga.

The earlier part of the inscription before the introduction of the feudatory family of the Chāhamānas, to which the donor Anaya-simha belonged, may be divided into two sections, the first containing invocation to various deities and the second the genealogy of the Imperial Paramāras of Malwa. The first section begins with the *Pranava* and a passage in prose in adoration to Dharma described as *purush-ārtha-hūdāmaṇi*. The same invocation is found in several other grants of the Paramāra kings.² The above is followed by eleven stanzas (verses 1-11) in adoration of the following deities: 'the lord of sacrificers', i.e. the Moon-god (verse 1) who is similarly invoked at the beginning of some other Paramāra charters;³ Rāma, i.e. Paraśurāma (verse 2); Rāma, i.e. Rāma Dāśarathi (verse 3); Purandruha, i.e. Śiva (verse 4); Śarva having eight forms, i.e. Śiva (verse 5); Ōṅkāra (verse 6), identical with Paśupati or Śiva and having his temple on the bank of the Rēvā or Narmadā (verse 7), the description of the shrine near the junction of the Rēvā and the Kāvērī being continued in the following stanza (verse 8); Kaiṭabhajit or Viṣṇu in his Boar incarnation (verse 10); and Pitāmaha, i.e. Brahman (verse 11).

The said section is followed by the mythical account of the origin of the Paramāra dynasty. Verse 12 relates how the god Brahman created out of his own mind the Seven Sages, one of whom was Vasishṭha. The next stanza (verse 13) refers to the quarrel between Vasishṭha and Kauśika, i.e. Viśvāmitra, wellknown from the epics and Purāṇas, while verse 14 states how Vasishṭha created out of his sacrificial fire-pit a hero named Paramāra for punishing his foes (i.e. Viśvāmitra's forces) who were the enemies of Dharma. Verse 15 says that this Paramāra was the progenitor of a royal family [bearing his name]. This mythical account of the origin of the Paramāras is first noticed in records of the eleventh century⁴ when it seems to have been fabricated. The myth has been interpreted to mean that the Paramāras were Hinduised foreigners of the Hūṇa-Gurjara stock.⁵ The theory is of course not disproved by the evidence of the Harsola plates,⁶ according to which Bappairāja (Vākpatirāja I) was descended from the family of the Rāshtrakūṭa king Akālavarsha Kṛishṇa III (939-66 A.D.), since this apparently refers to Bappairāja's relations with the Rāshtrakūṭa house on his mother's side as otherwise, if the Paramāras were direct des-

¹ *JASB*, Vol. V, 1836, pp. 377-82.

² Cf. above, Vol. IX, pp. 108 (text line 1), 120 (text line 1).

³ *Ibid.*, pp. 108 (text lines 1-2, verse 1), 120 (text lines 1-2, verse 1).

⁴ Cf. above, Vol. XIV, pp. 295 ff.; *Navasāha-ānkacharita*, XI, 64 ff.

⁵ Tod, *Annals and Antiquities of Rajasthan*, ed. Crooke, Vol. I, pp. 112 ff.; Cunningham, *ASR*, Vol. II, pp. 254 ff., etc.

⁶ Above, Vol. XIX, pp. 239-40; cf. Ray, *op. cit.*, pp. 841-42.

cendants of the Rāshtrakūṭa emperors, the Paramāra rulers would have continued to mention the fact even in their later records.

The above account of the mythical origin of the Paramāra family is followed by a long list of Paramāra kings ending with the ruler, during whose reign the charter under study was issued. There are altogether 24 names in this section, the first 9 of which are unhistorical. These imaginary names are : Kamaṇḍaludhara, king of Dhārā (verse 16) : his son Dhūmarāja whose name was justified by the smoke arising from the cities of his enemies that were burnt by him (verses 17-18) : his son Dēvasimhapāla (verse 19) : his son Kanakasiṃha (verse 20) : his son Śrīharsha (verse 20a) : Jagaddēva king of Mālava (verses 21-22) ; Sthirakāya (verse 23) ; Vōsari, lord of Dhārā (verse 24) ; and his son Vīrasimha (verse 25). These names forming a group are introduced in the genealogy of the Imperial Paramāras for the first time in the present record. Of the nine names, Dhūmarāja seems to have been adopted from the genealogy of the Paramāras of Arbuda¹ while Vīrasimha, although he is called the son of an imaginary Vōsari, may be a modification of the name of Vairisimha who was the father of Vākpati I mentioned in our inscription in the following stanza (verse 26). A king named Jagaddēva no doubt flourished in the family, but at a much later date than the period indicated by our inscription.² There was no Śrīharsha in the family, who was the son and successor of a king named Kanakasiṃha.³ It will be seen that imagination and confusion have both played a part in the genealogy of the Imperial Paramāras quoted above from the inscription under study.

Verses 26-56 give the names of 15 Paramāra rulers of the Imperial house, although some of the kings have been omitted. Vākpatirāja is mentioned in verse 26 as famous for his *sūktis* in the Prakrit language : but the well-known literary merits of his great-grandson Muñja (Vākpati II) who is separately mentioned in verses 28-29 of our record, appear to be reflected in this statement. Verse 27 mentions Sīyā (i.e. Sīyaka *alias* Śrī-Harsha, c. 948-74 A.D.) who was the grandson of Vākpati, and omits Vākpati's son Vairisimha *alias* Vajraṭa. The next two stanzas (verses 28-29) describe Muñja (who was the son and successor of Sīyaka and ruled in c. 974-95 A.D.) without specifically mentioning his relations with Sīyā, while verses 30-31 mention Sindhurāja (who was the brother and successor of Muñja and ruled in c. 995-1010 A.D.) similarly without stating his relations with Muñja. The following four stanzas (verses 32-35) describe the achievements of Bhōja (c. 1010-55 A.D.), son of Sindhurāja, in vague terms. Verse 36 passes over Bhōja's son and successor Jayasimha (c. 1055-60 A.D.) and mentions Udayāditya (c. 1060-90 A.D.) who appears to have been a distant cousin of Bhōja. Udayāditya is stated to have recovered the kingdom from the Gūrjara king. This reference to the Gūrjara occupation of Malwa no doubt alludes to the Paramāra king's struggle with the Chaulukyas of Gujarāt. According to the *Ras Mālā*, supported by the *Prabandhachintāmaṇi*, Kalachuri Karṇa (c. 1041-72 A.D.) of Dāhala and Chaulukya Bhīma (c. 1022-64 A.D.) of Gujarāt jointly attacked king Bhōja of Ujjayinī, defeated and killed him and destroyed the city of Dhārā.⁴ The reference may also be to Udayāditya's struggle with Chaulukya Karṇa I (c. 1064-94 A.D.), son of Bhīma I. While a Chitorgarh inscription⁵ of

¹ See above. pp. 135 ff.

² Jagaddēva *alias* Lakshmadēva was a son of Udayāditya (known dates between V.S. 1116=1060 A.D. and V.S. 1143=1087 A.D.) and his known date is V.S. 1151 (1097 A.D.) when, according to a bardic tradition, he offered his head to the goddess Kālī (cf. Bhandarkar's List, p. 397).

³ The Paramāra king Sīyaka *alias* Śrī-Harsha (known dates between V.S. 1005=949 A.D. and V.S. 1029=973 A.D.) succeeded his father Vairisimha *alias* Vajraṭa (loc. cit.) and he is apparently mentioned as Sīyā in verse 27 of our inscription.

⁴ See Ray, op. cit., pp. 777-78.

⁵ Above, Vol. XX, p. 209, Nos. 15-22.

Kumārapāla's time merely credits Karṇa I with a victory over the Mālavas at the Sūdakūpa pass, the *Prithvirājarājya*, *Sukṛitasamkīrtana* and *Surathōtsava* refer to his conquest of the Mālava country.¹ An inscription² in the Nagpur Museum refers to Udayāditya's conquest of the earth (i.e. the Paramāra kingdom) which had been occupied, jointly with the Karṇātas, by Karṇa who is identified by some scholars with Chaulukya Karṇa I but by others with the Kalachuri king of Dāhala bearing the same name.³

Verses 36-37 speak of Naravarman (c. 1101-1135 A.D.), son of Udayālitva, but pass over his elder brother Lakshmadēva or Jagaddēva (c. 1090-1101 A.D.) in silence. The next stanza (verse 39) mentions Yaśōvarman (c. 1135-45 A.D.) without specifying the fact that he was the son and successor of Naravarman. Verses 40-41 speak of Ajayavarman, son of Yaśōvarman,⁴ while the next two stanzas describe Ajayavarman's son Vindhavarman (verse 42) and grandson Subhatavarman (verse 43) without stating the fact that Subhatavarman was the son and successor of Vindhavarman. Arjunadēva (i.e. Arjunavarman, known dates between V.S. 1267 and 1270, i.e. 1211-15 A.D.), son of Subhatavarman, is mentioned in verses 44-45, in the first of which he is described as devoted to Kṛishṇa.

There is a valuable reference to a historical event in verses 46-48 in the description of the next king **Dēvapāla** (known dates between V.S. 1275 and 1289, i.e. 1218-32 A.D.) who is mentioned without specifying his relationship with Arjunavarman. Dēvapāla belonged to a branch of the Paramāra family, being the grandson of *Mahākumāra* Lakshmīvarman (known date V.S. 1200, i.e. 1144 A.D.) who was a brother of king Ajayavarman of the main line. In the branch line, ruling independently over the region about Bhopal, Indore, Hoshangabad, Khandesh and Nimar, Lakshmīvarman was succeeded as *Mahākumāra* by his son Hariśchandra (known dates V.S. 1235-36, i.e. 1179-81 A.D.) whose successor was his son *Mahākumāra* Udayavarman (known date V.S. 1256, i.e. 1200 A.D.). Dēvapāla was the younger brother and successor of Udayavarman. With Dēvapāla's accession to the throne of Arjunavarman of the main branch of the Paramāra family, the two parts of the Paramāra kingdom became reunited.

Verse 48 states that Dēvapāla killed an *adhīpa* (i.e. a king or chief) of the **Mlēchchhas** in a battle fought near the city of **Bhailasvāmin**. This no doubt refers to the invasion of the city of Bhailasvāmin (modern Bhīlsā) by Iltutmish (1212-36 A.D.), the Turkish Sultān of Delhi. According to Muslim historians, in 632 A.H. or 1233-34 A.D., Iltutmish reduced Gwalior to subjection and turned his arms against Malwa : he captured the fort of Bhīlsā where the temple of Bhailasvāmin was demolished and marched into Ujjayinī where he destroyed the great temple of the god Mahākāla.⁵ The claim of Dēvapāla in the stanza of our inscription, referred to above, seems to suggest that the Paramāra king succeeded in recovering the city of Bhīlsā shortly after its conquest by Iltutmish. The Mlēchchhādhipa mentioned in the verse was probably the Muslim governor in whose charge the city was placed by the Sultān. That the Paramāras reconquered Bhīlsā is also suggested by the fact that, after half a century, the Khaljī Sultāns of Delhi had to reconquer the city from the Hindus.⁶

¹ Cf. Ganguly, op. cit., pp. 130-31.

² Above, Vol. II, pp. 185, 192 (verse 32); cf. ibid., Vol. I, pp. 236, 238 (verses 21-22).

³ See Ganguly, op. cit., p. 130.

⁴ Some scholars believe that Yaśōvarman's elder son named Jayavarman was overthrown by his younger son named Ajayavarman, while others believe that Jayavarman and Ajayavarman were two different names of one and the same king. See Ray, op. cit., pp. 888 ff.; Ganguly, op. cit., pp. 181 ff.

⁵ See Elliot and Dowson, *History of India*, Vol. II, 328; *Tarikh-i-Firishta*, Briggs' trans., Vol. I, p. 211; *Tabaqat-i-Nāṣirī*, Raverty's trans., Vol. I, p. 622.

⁶ *Tārīkh-i-Firishta*, op. cit., pp. 303-04.

Dēvapāla's son and successor was Jaitugi (known dates V.S. 1292-1300, i.e. 1236-44 A.D.) mentioned in verse 49. Verses 50-56 describe the Paramāra king during whose rule the charter under discussion was issued. He was the younger brother of Jaitugi; but the relationship between the two is not indicated in our record. It is interesting to note that he is called **Jayavarman** in verses 50 and 56 (as well as in line 87 and verse 72 below) but **Jayasimha** in verses 51-52. This king was so far known under the name Jayavarman (it is doubtful whether the name is Jayasimha in one of the cases) from the following inscriptions of his time: (1) Rahatgarh stone inscription¹ of V.S. 1312 (1256 A.D.); (2) Modi stone inscription² of V.S. 1314 (1258 A.D.), and (3) Māndhātā plates³ of V.S. 1317 (1261 A.D.). The Pathari inscription⁴ of V.S. 1326 (1269 A.D.) belongs to the reign of a Paramāra king named Jayasimha and there is a controversy amongst scholars whether Jayavarman mentioned in the Rahatgarh, Modi and Māndhātā records is identical with Jayasimha of the Pathari inscription.⁵ That a Paramāra king named Jayasimha ruled from Maṇḍapa some time before V.S. 1345 (1289 A.D.) is also suggested by the Balvan inscription⁶ of Chāhamāna Hammīra of Raṇastambhapura as his father Jaitrasimha who died in V.S. 1339 (1283 A.D.) is stated to have defeated the said king. The present inscription, dated V. S. 1331 (1274 A.D.) and mentioning the Paramāra king by both the names Jayavarman and Jayasimha, shows clearly that scholars like Ganguly who regard Jayasimha of the Pathari inscription as different from Jayavarman of the Rahatgarh, Modi and Māndhātā (V.S. 1317) inscriptions are wrong. Ray's suggestion⁷ that Jaitugi may have also been known by the name Jayasimha is equally wrong since the two brothers, Jaitugi and Jayavarman, could not both of them have enjoyed the common name Jayasimha. The rule of Paramāra Jayasimha-Jayavarman may be assigned to the period 1255-75 A.D.

Verse 52 of our inscription seems to suggest that Jayasimha-Jayavarman was regarded as both a *dauhitra* (daughter's son) and a *putra* (son's son) with reference to his succession to the Paramāra throne. This statement seems to throw some light on the controversy whether Dēvapāla of a branch line of the family succeeded Arjunavarman of the main line by overthrowing the latter by violence or because Arjunavarman died without leaving any male heir.⁸ If the stanza in question means to say that Jayasimha-Jayavarman claimed to be a *dauhitra* of Arjunavarman, Dēvapāla may be regarded as having succeeded Arjunavarman as the latter's son-in-law and heir.

Verse 54 speaks of Jayasimha-Jayavarman's success against the king of **Dākshinātya** lying to the south of the Vindhya. This may refer to his struggle with the Yādava king Rāmachandra who, according to his Thana plates⁹ of Śaka 1194 (1272 A.D.), defeated the Mālavas. The Udari stone inscription¹⁰ of the same king, dated Śaka 1198 (1276 A.D.), speaks of his victory over king Arjuna of Mālava, who was apparently the immediate successor of Jayasimha-Jayavarman and may be regarded as Arjunavarman II. The same Paramāra king is also mentioned in the Balvan

¹ Cunningham, *ASR*, Vol. X, p. 31.

² *ASIH C*, 1905, p. 12; *ibid.*, 1913, p. 56.

³ Above, Vol. IX, pp. 117-23.

⁴ Bhandarkar's List, No. 575.

⁵ See *ibid.*, p. 397, and Ray, *op. cit.*, p. 905, for one view, and Ganguly, *op. cit.*, p. 227, for another.

⁶ Bhandarkar's List, No. 623.

⁷ *Op. cit.*, p. 928.

⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 902.

⁹ Above, Vol. XIII, pp. 202-03.

¹⁰ *An. Rep. Arch. Surv. Mys.* 1929, p. 143.

inscription¹ (V.S. 1345=1288 A.D.) of Chāhamāna Hammīra (c. 1283-1301 A.D.) of Raṇastambhapura. Hammīra is stated to have defeated Arjuna in battle and wrested the glory of Mālava by force.²

According to lines 128 ff., the four villages, having well-defined boundaries, were granted as a permanent endowment together with trees, houses, house-sites, granaries and threshing floors, *tala-bhēdhyā* (pits ?) and cow-sheds. The donees' rights included certain taxes payable by the tenants in kind and described as handfuls of vegetables, small measures of oil and vesselfuls of liquids or grains. They were granted the right over objects grown in the space above the earth and treasures and deposits under the ground as well as over temples, gardens, tanks, step-wells, wells, etc. They were further allowed to enjoy taxes in cash, periodical offerings and the customary share of grains, and also the tax on temporary tenants as well as other incomes including fines. But the donees were not allowed to have any right over any part of the land already in the possession of gods and Brāhmaṇas. The *Pattakilas* and villagers were ordered to pay to the donees the usual share of the produce, periodical offerings and taxes in cash as well as to obey their orders. Some of the ordinary imprecatory and benedictory stanzas are quoted in lines 134-38. According to verse 72 in line 139, the writer of the charter was Śrikanṭha who was a courtier of king Jayavarman. The document was engraved by *Rūpakāra* (artisan) Kānhāka who may be the same as Kānhāḍa, the engraver of the Māndhātā plates of V.S. 1317 (1261 A.D.), issued by the same king.

The following **geographical** names are mentioned in the inscription : (1) Rēvā, i.e. the river Narmadā ; (2) Kāvērī, a branch of the Narmadā ; (3) Māndhātri or Māndhātri-durga, i.e. modern Māndhātā ; (4) Dhārā, i.e. modern Dhār ; (5) Bhaillasvānipura, i.e. modern Bhīlsā ; (6) the Vindhya mountain range ; (7) Dākshīṇātya, apparently meaning the dominions of the Yādavas of Dēvagiri ; (8) Dēvapālapura, probably modern Dipalpur, 27 miles to the north-west of Mhow ; (9) Śākapura probably the headquarters of a Pratiḷāgaraṇaka or Pargana of the same name identified by some with the present Shujalpur Pargana ;³ (10) Maṇḍapa-durga, i.e. modern Māṇḍū ; (11) Vardhanā-pura-pratiḷāgaraṇaka ; (12) Kumbhaḍāuda-grāma ; (13) Vālauda-grāma ; (14) Saptāśīti-pratiḷāgaraṇaka, literally 'a Pargana consisting of 87 villages' ; (15) Vaghāḍī-grāma ; (16) Nāgadaha-pratiḷāgaraṇaka, a Pargana probably having its headquarters at Nagdah near Ujjain ; (17) Nāṭiyā-

¹ Bhandarkar's List, No. 623.

² The successor of Arjunavarman II on the Paramāra throne seems to have been Bhōja II. According to the *Hammīramahākāvya* of Nayachandra, Chāhamāna Hammīra of Raṇastambhapura also defeated king Bhōja of Dhārā, encamped at Ujjayinī and worshipped Mahākāla (*Ind. Ant.*, Vol. VIII, pp. 64-65). The Muslim writers speak of one Kōkā (sometimes called Haranand), the Rājā of Malwa, who was defeated by 'Alāuddīn Khaljī in 1305, A.D. (*Tarikh-i-Firishta*, Briggs' trans., Vol. I, pp. 361-62 ; Ray, op. cit., pp. 907-08). In an inscription of V.S. 1496 (Bhandarkar's List, No. 784) the same ruler is called Gōgādeva, king of Mālava, who was defeated by Guhila Lakshmasimha, a contemporary of the Khaljī Sultān. Kōkā thus appears to have been either identical with or a contemporary of Bhōja II. Wassāf, who wrote his *Taziyatul Amsār* in 1300 A.D., says : " It may be about thirty years previous to my laying the foundation of this book that the king of Malwa died and dissension arose between his son and minister. After long hostilities and much slaughter, each of them acquired possession of part of that country " (Elliot and Dowson, op. cit., Vol. III, p. 31). It is not impossible that the king of Malwa and his son referred to here are Arjunavarman II and Bhōja II. In such a case, Kōkā may be the minister who became the king of a part of Malwa at the time of Bhōja II during whose reign Wassāf seems to have written his book. Muslim authors sometimes call Kōkā a *Pradhān* of king Mahlak Deo of Malwa (Elliot and Dowson op. cit., p. 76). This Mahlak Deo may have been the successor of Bhōja II. He was probably succeeded by Jayasimha whose Udaypur inscription (Bhandarkar's List, No. 661) is dated in V.S. 1366 (1310 A.D.). But Jayasimha must have been ruling over a part of the country, its other parts then being in the hands of the Muslim conquerors.

³ Ganguly, op. cit., p. 201.

grāma (modern Nāvṭiyā near the Birwania railway station in the Ujjain District.); (18) Ṭakārī;¹ (19) Lakhaṇapura; (20) Tōlāpauha; (21) Ṭēṇī; (22) Mālava, i.e. the dominions of the Paramāras roughly comprising modern Malwa; and (23) Bhārata, i.e. India.

TEXT²

[Metres: Verses 1, 39 *Upajāti*; verses 2, 5, 9-10, 22, 29, 31, 38, 45, 47-48, 52, 54-55, 60 *Śārdūla-vikrīḍita*; verses 3, 18-19, 44, 63 *Gīti*; verses 4, 13, 16-17, 20A, 23-25, 27, 32, 34-35, 37, 40, 42, 46, 49-51, 53, 56-57, 61-62, 68-69, 72 *Anushtubh*; verses 7, 33, 41, 46, 72 *Sragdharā*; verses 6, 8, 26, 58, 64 *Āryā*; verses 11, 36 *Harīṇī*; verse 12 *Śikhariṇī*; verses 14, 28, 65, 67 *Vasantatilaka*; verses 15, 20-21, 43 *Mālinī*; verse 30 *Upēndravajrā*; verse 59 *Upagīti*; verse 70 *Śālinī*; verse 71 *Pushpitāgrā*.]

First Plate

- 1 || Ō namaḥ puruṣa-ārtha-chūḍā-maṇayē Dharmāyā(ya |) Pratigraha[m*] yō virachayya lakṣmīm=udirṇṇa-varṇṇō jagad=ujjihānaḥ [|*] āna[m*]da-
- 2 yaty=ētaḍ=uru-prasādaḥ sa yajvanām=astu patiḥ priyāya³ ||1 Kṛitvā lēkhanikām kuṭhāram=udaya-dvāram(rē) niyuddh-āsvarō⁴ yaḥ kshatra-ksha-
- 3 tajāta-jāta-sumakhīm(shīm) mēlamvam⁵=ambhōnidhim | patram digvalayam svam=aksharachaṇam nirvarttayan=śāsanam viprēbhyah prithivīm=adā-
- 4 d=udayinīm Rāmāya tasmai namaḥ || 2 [A]śrānt-āsram(sra)-payōbhir=laṅghana-vam(bam)dh-ābhimānajā[m] jaladhēḥ | kṛisatām śamayitum=iva yō
- 5 rakshāmsy=avadhīn=namāmi tam Rāman(mam) ||3 Śarībhūya⁶ Hariḥ kukshi-nikshiptabhuvana-trayaḥ | yad-aṅguli-dalē tasthau namas=tasmai
- 6 Puradruhē ||4 Bhūmīm bhūtimayīm=apaḥ Surasarid-rūpās=ṭṛitīy-ēkshana-jvāl-ābham jvalanam bhujastha-bhujaga-śvās-ātmakam mā-
- 7 rutam(tam) | kham raṁdhrēshu kapāla-dāmani nayana-dvaita-chchhalāt=pūshanaṁ chaṁdraṁ svam yajamānam=ity=avatu vaḥ Śarvvō=shṭa vi(bi)bhranta(t=ta)nuḥ(nūḥ) ||5 Dēvānām
- 8 vēdānām trayasya y[ō] jāta-vēdasām jagatām(tām) | lēbhē nām=ādima iti namāmi dēvam tam=Ōmkāram(ram) || 6 Śambhōr=a[m]bhōbhir=asya
- 9 snapana-vidhi-vasā(sā)d=apy=aham mūrddhanī(ni) dvē saṁdhānam(nē) sa[m]vidhāsy[ā] dhruvam=iti vidhurā Svardhunī-sparddhay=ēva | Rēvā sēv-ānushaṅgād=i-
- 10 va charaṇa-tal-ālamvi(bi)nī yasya bhāti prāsād[ō]=bhramliha-śrī[r*]=jam(ja)yati Pasu(śu)-patēḥ sō=yam=Ōmkāra-nāmnā || 7 Yat-prāsād-āgra-
- 11 [ka]lasa-tāḍita-pūrā Surāpagā mukharā | Rēv-ānushaṅga-rōsha(shā)d=iva Gaṅgādham=upālabhatē || 8 Nō gamyō Yama-kimkarair=nna du-
- 12 ritair=āsādanīyō na vā dhṛishyō mōha-mahōrmmibhir=nna Kalinā ch=aisha pravēshṭum kshamaḥ | matvā kuṁḍalanām=iv=ēti paritaḥ

¹ For this place, see above, Vol. XXIX, p. 86.

² From a set of impressions.

³ The adoration to the Moon-god also occurs in other Paramāra inscriptions including the Māndhātā ; la es of V.S. 1317, issued by the same king. See above, Vol. IX, p. 120.

⁴ Read °adhvarē.

⁵ Read mēl-āmbum°.

⁶ Vishṇu became the arrow with which Śiva killed the demon Tripura. See *Saura Purāna*, 35, 16; *Śiva Purāna*, Jñāna-saṁhitā, 24, 11.

2 | ...
 4 | ...
 6 | ...
 8 | ...
 10 | ...
 12 | ...
 14 | ...
 16 | ...
 18 | ...
 20 | ...

2 4 6 8 10 12 14 16 18 20

Scale : Two-fifths

- 13 saṁprāpitō Rēvayā Kāvēryā¹ cha Pitāmahēna sumahān -Māndhātṛi-dhātṛīdharah ||9 Muktau-
(ktai)r=yāsyati kutrachid=vasumatī daṁshṭr-āgra-
- 14 saṁśa(sa)rggiṇī kukshau kshōbham=avāpsyati tri-bhuvanaṁ ruddhair -amībhir -bhṛīśau(śam)
| ity=a-svalpa-vikalpa-mīlita-matēḥ kaṁṭhē lūṭhant[ō]
- 15 muhuḥ kōl-ākāra-dharasya Mai(Kai)ṭabhajitah śvās-ōrmmayah pāntu vah ||10 Nigama-
vadanām Vēdāṅg-āṅgīm Purāṇama[y-ē]tara-sphura-
- 16 d-avayavām vakratv-ōktiṁ kavitva-tanū-ruhām(hām) | pada-padavatīm vāky-ātumāam
pramāṇamay-āśayām tanum=iti navām vi(bi)bhrad-bhrāntīm
- 17 bhinattu Pitāmahaḥ ||11 Sa nābhēḥ saṁbhūya svavaṁ iha Murārēḥ jagad idam sasarja
prādhānyāt=kiyaḍ-āpi tataḥ srasṭu-
- 18 m=aparam(ram) | munīn=mānyān-sapta vyarachayaḍ-ayaṁ svīya-manasō Vasishṭā(shtthō)-
bhūd=ēshām tapasi kṛita-niḥkaṁ(niḥkaṁ)pa-niyamaḥ ||12 Sa yadā [n ā]-
- 19 karōt=kōpam=āpi putra-śatē hatē | tad=ābhyashēṇayad=dra[shṭuṁ] tapō sya kila Kauśikah
||13 Tēn=ātha māraya parān=i-
- 20 ti jalpatā yat=sṛiṣṭas=tadā muni-varēṇa kṛīśānu-kunḍāt | dharmmā(rmma)-[dru]hām
viśasanād=iha yōga-
- 21 tō=pi khyātas=tataḥ sa[ma][bha*]vat-Paramāra-nāmā ||14 Samajani [ki]la tasmād=ōsha
rājanya-

Second Plate, First Side

- 22 vaṁśah sakala-dharaṇi-dhu[rya]-prāmsu(śu)-vaṁś-āvataṁśah(sah) | avatarati na yasmin=
jātu Vishṇōr=anaṁśah para-dha-
- 23 raṇi-bhujām vā mānasē yō na ha[n]śah(sah) ||15 Kamarūdaludharō Dhār-ādhiśas=tatra
kramād=a[bhūt [*] Yaśōbhiḥ śōbhi-
- 24 tē yasya svasthō=bhūd=bhūtalē vidhu[h] ||16 Tātē tatra prapannē=tha nāki-nāyaka-vai-
bhavaṁ(vam) | Dhūmarājō bhavad rājā pratāpais-tapana-
- 25 prabhah ||17 Dahatī pratyaham-uchchai[h] pratīpa-nṛipa-pura-parampa[rā]m=iti yah [[*]
dhūma-dhyāmair-uditō gagana-charair- Dhūmarāja iti
- 26 nāmnā || 18 Atha D[ē]vasiṁhapālas- tasmād=asmīn-abhūn=nṛipō bhuvanō [[*] yasya pratāpa-
tapanah prati-nṛipati-tamaḥ kshayaṁ kshaṇād ana-
- 27 yat ||19 Svar-adhivasati Dhārā-tīrtha-gatyā sva-tāt[ē] jayati Kanakasīnhas=tatra rājyō
kramēṇa | bhavati kila talē-sya sva[h*] pitā
- 28 mē prasāṅgād=iti khalu vitaran-yō dhō- vyadhāt=Kalpa-vṛiksham(ksham) ||20 Śrī-Hara-
rshō²=bhūn-nṛipas tasmād=atha prathita-pō(pau)rusha[h [*] dānavān akarōt sa-
- 29 rrvān=sukhinō Vaishṇōpi yah³ || 20A*] Sva-pada-vinimayēna svas-tam=āsajya rājyō kshiti-
tala-vijihīrshā-kautukān nākināthah | a[bha]-
- 30 vad-a[tha] Jagaddēva⁴ ity-ākhyay=ōdyat-kara-kṛita-karavālō Mālava-kshōṇi-kha[m]ḍē ||21
Karṇṇah karṇṇa-kaṭuh Śivirṇṇa(r-nna) si(śi)va-dō Vai-

¹ This is the name of a northern branch of the Narmadā (Rēvā) near Māndhātā (compared with the epic king bearing the same name) where the Ōnkārēśvara temple stands.

² Read *Harshō* .

³ Read *Vaiśṇavō=pi yah*. The number of this stanza is omitted in the original.

⁴ The passage is metrically defective.

- 31 rōchanē n=ōchitā— — —¹ ya-vanīpakē vinayatē chintām na Chintāmaṇiḥ | svalpaḥ Kalpa-
tarur=na Kāma-surabhiḥ kāma-prapūrtyai purō
- 32 yasmin=sa-smitam=arthi-sārtha-manasām=ichchh-ādhiḥkām yachchhati ||22 Sthira-dhī Sthira-
k[ā*]yō=tha prājyam rājyam prapannavan(vān) | sthira-kāyō=
- 33 sya [tu*] yuddhai(dddhē)shv=iti s-ārthaka-samjñayā ||2[3] Tatō Vōsarir=ity=āsīddhā(d=Dhā)r-
ādhipatir=uddhataḥ | yēna yuddhē hatair= vvīraiḥ samvā(bā)dhā
- 34 dyaurṇṇa(r=nna) v=āmarai[h*] || 24 Vīrasimhas=tatō vīra-rasika(kō) rasik-āsayaḥ |
pitur-yō rājyam=āsādya jigāya jagatīm=imām(mām) || 25
- 35 Vākpatirājō rājyē tasminn=āsīn=mahītalē mahati | yasya Prākṛita-sūktibhir=arajyata prā-
kṛitō lōkaḥ ||26 Chaturām
- 36 chatur-ambhōdhi-paridhēr=adhipam bhuvah [*] Sīyā-nāmānam=atr-ātha sāmra(mrā)jya-
śrīr=asīśriyat ||27 Ujvā(jjvā)ka-tōjasi yasō(śō)-visē(śa)dē=
- 37 tha vanīsē tasmin=mahān-ajani Muñja iti kshiti² kshit-īśaḥ | sparddhā-vasū(śā)d-iva
mithaḥ samitau kṛipāṇaḥ pāṇis=cha dānam=a-
- 38 tanōd=adhikām yadiyaḥ ||28 Gāyaty=amtar-amaṇda-samṇada-bharā visrām(śrām)ta-
harsh-āśrubhiḥ pūrṇṇ-āṇchat-puta-rlō(lō)chan-āṇchalatayā n=ā-
- 39 lōkya kāntām puraḥ | maṇḍāra-stava(ba)k-āvataṇśa(sa)-vilasad-rōlānva(ba)-kōlāhala-
sphāyan-nādam=uditvaram sura-vadhūḥ kīrtim yadiyām
- 40 divi ||29 Tataḥ sphurat-saṅgara-sam[ga*]-raṅgam=abhaṅgur-āṅgam kila Simdhurāja[m]-
(jam |) sad-ōditām sādaram=āsasāda prabhutva-lakshmīḥ pratata-pratā-
- 41 pam(pam) ||30 Yam sārasvatam=ādadhānam=amṛitam prakhyāta-ratn-ōtkaram sat-paksha-
kshītibhrih-chharaṇyam=uditām prāyaḥ prasā(sā)d-āspadam(dam) | san-maryāda-
- 42 m-agādham=āyata-padam vyāpta-kshamā-maṇḍalam satya[m] jalpati Simdhurājam=akhilāḥ
prōdya[d*]-dvij-ōllāsitam(tam) ||31 Simdhurājād=a-
- 43 bhūt=tasmāt=kalānām pātram=udyataḥ [*] bhāsayan kumudam Bhōjarājō rājā prasāda-
bhū[h*] ||32 Arthi-pratyarthi-sārthā(rtha)-sthita-

Second Plate, Second Side

- 44 kara-nikar-ōpātta-[sam]nyasta-ma[tta]-prājya-prōddāma-damṭāvala-va(ba)hala-galad-dāna-
tōy-ōdbhavishṇuḥ | ya[d*]-dvāri dvāstha-mukhya-kshaṇa-dhṛita-
- 45 dharāṇipāla-niśvāsa-rāsi-sphūrjjad-vātyā-pratānaiḥ prachuram=api pu[na|h] śushkatām=
ēti pamkaḥ³ || 33 Śamva(ba)rāri-śaraiḥ pūrva-janman=i-
- 46 ha nij-ēshuṇā | Rādham vivyādha yaḥ prāyaḥ prathayann=Achyut-ātmatām(tām) ||34 Yaḥ
kurvvan=mārgaṇān=rājñāḥ parān=rājñāś=cha mārgaṇan(ṇān) | sarva-
- 47 sva-tyāga-yōgēna parivartakatām dadhau ||35 Udayam=Udayādityaḥ prāpa pratāpa-nidhis=
ta[tō] ripu-nṛipa-tama-stōmān=astam naya-
- 48 n=vilasat-karaḥ [*] udaharata yō dōr-ddamshṭrābhyām sad-ūrjjita-Gūrjjara-kshītīpa-
jaladhau magnām=ētā[m*] Vā(Va)rāha iv=āvanim(nim) || 36 Naravarmma ta-

¹ Three syllables are omitted here due to carelessness of the scribe or engraver.

² These two letters are redundant.

³ There is an *anusvāra* above *kaḥ*. The intended reading is *°bhavishṇu.....paṅkam*.

ii, b

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Scale : Two-fifths

68 70 72 74 76 78 80 82 84 86 88

...वक्रैः सङ्घट्टयति मत्तम् ॥ ७७ ॥
 ...सिद्धं तदा न पुनर्विद्यते ॥ ७८ ॥
 ...मन्त्रैः सङ्घट्टयति मत्तम् ॥ ७९ ॥
 ...सिद्धं तदा न पुनर्विद्यते ॥ ८० ॥
 ...मन्त्रैः सङ्घट्टयति मत्तम् ॥ ८१ ॥
 ...सिद्धं तदा न पुनर्विद्यते ॥ ८२ ॥
 ...मन्त्रैः सङ्घट्टयति मत्तम् ॥ ८३ ॥
 ...सिद्धं तदा न पुनर्विद्यते ॥ ८४ ॥
 ...मन्त्रैः सङ्घट्टयति मत्तम् ॥ ८५ ॥
 ...सिद्धं तदा न पुनर्विद्यते ॥ ८६ ॥
 ...मन्त्रैः सङ्घट्टयति मत्तम् ॥ ८७ ॥
 ...सिद्धं तदा न पुनर्विद्यते ॥ ८८ ॥

68 70 72 74 76 78 80 82 84 86 88

- 49 tō rāja-ratnam ratn-ākarān=ṛi[paḥ | jāta]ḥ sva-tējas=ākrānta-sarvv-ōrvvī-bhartṛi-bhū-
shanē(ṇaḥ) ||37 Utkhātāḥ para-bhūmayāḥ punar=amūr=āttās=tatō=
- 50 bhyu[d*]dhrītā drāgnihkamṭakitāḥ¹ karaiḥ parichitās=chakrē nijē rōpitāḥ | pātr-ārtham
ghaṭitāḥ sva-sūtra-kalitāḥ snigdhiḥkṛitā yatnatō
- 51 yēn=ēti prakāṣam kulāla-charita-krīdāsu na vrīditam(tam) ||38 Tatō Yaśōvarmmā(rmma)-
nṛipō va(ba)bhūva prachamḍa-dōr-ddamḍa-lasaj-jaya-śrīḥ | mā-
- 52 ty=arddham=ādyam na kim(ki)la trilōkyām dvitīyam=amgē yudhi yasya nāmnaḥ ||39
Tasmād=Ajayavarmm-ābhūd=bhū[ta]lē bhūmi-vallabha[h] | pratā-
- 53 pa-tapanō yasya kamal-ōllāsan-ōlvaṇaḥ ||40 Prabhrasyan-muṇḍa-mālam skhalita-gaja-
mukham vyagra-jāgrach-ehiv-āsyam vyākīrṇasthi²-prakāram
- 54 dhuta-vidhura-mahāsēnam -udbh[r*]jānta-bhūtam(tam) | dhvast=ōchchaiḥ-kṛitti-khamḍam
prapatita-nayana-śrōtram=ugr-ōgra-bhā[va]m yatsha(t-kha)ḍgēna vyadhāyi pravana(ṇa)m=a-
- 55 nudinam raṅga-bhūr=Bhairavasya ||41 Viṇḍhyavarmm=ābhavat=tasmād=asminn=urvvī-talē=
khilē | yō Viṇḍhya-giri-[va]d=vairi-nṛip-ōpāyana-damtibhiḥ
- 56 || 42 Ajani Subhaṭavarmmā saṅgarē krūra-karmmā kshata-ripu-nṛipa-varmmā saṅsadi
prāpta-śarmmā | tridasa(śa)-pati-sadharmm=āth=āṅgan-ō-
- 57 dgīta-narmmō(rmmā) ruchita-ruchira-varmmā mārgaṇa-prāpta-kharmmā³ ||43 Arjjunadēvas=
tasmād=Arjjuna iva Karṇa-jitvarō dānē | Bhārata-bhūshā-
- 58 bhāvī Kṛishṇa-aika-ratirva(r-ba)bhūva bhū-bharttā ||44 Satva(t-pa)ksha-kshitibhrij-jaya-
vyasanitām śrutv āsya nām-ānvayān Maina(nā)ka-pramukhāḥ prakāṣpam=a-
- 59 dadhur-mmādhyā-mvu⁴ bhītā dhruvam(vam) | śrī-Sōmēsva(śva)ra-pabhṛivamḍha⁵-samayē
prakshutya(bhya)tō-mbhōniḍhēr=utkallōlatay=āvanau yad=abhavat=samvartta-kō-
- 60 lāhalah ||45 **Dēvapālas** tataḥ prāpa prājyam rājyam dhar-ādhipaḥ | sumanaḥ-saṅsadi
prītaḥ Kalpa-vṛiksh-ādi-madhyagaḥ ||46 Sphārai-
- 61 r-ullikhitē turāṅgama-khuraiḥ prauḍha-pratāp-ānalair=uddīptē=ri-vadhū-vilōchana-jalair=
līptē galat-kajjalaiḥ | yat-kāshṭhā-vi-
- 62 jayē vṛishaḥ khalu Kalāv=ēk-āṁhi(ghri)ṇā saṁcharan=pūtātvaḥ=charaṇais=chaturbhir=
adhunā bhū-mamḍalē kha(khē)lati | 47 Dhāvad-vāji-
- 63 khur-āgra-dhūta-vasudhā-prishtha-sphurad-dhūlija-dhvānt-ākrānta-dig-amtarāla-vishaya-
vyarthīkṛit-āhaskaram(ram) | **Bhailasvāmi**-pur-ōpa-
- 64 kamṭha-samarē Mlēcchēh-ādhipam durddharām yaḥ krōdhāt=taravāriṇ=aiva sahasā dvēdhā
vyadhād=uddhatam(tam) ||48 Tasmāj=Jaitugidēvō=bhūt-pā-
- 65 rthivaḥ pṛithivitalē | dharām-uddharatā yēna śrīmatā Śrīdhavāyita[m*] ||49 Tataḥ śrī-
Jayavarmmāṇam śīśri-
- 66 yē Śrīḥ sphuradbhū(d-bhu)jam(jam) | śrīr=dduryaśō yam-āsādya tatvāja chapal=ēty-
alam(lam) ||50 Yuga-yōgād=atikshīṇam vṛisha-

¹ Read *drān=niṣkamṭak dāh*.

² Read *vyākīrṇ-āsthi*.

³ The word is generally spelt as *kharma* and not *kharmam*.

⁴ Read *°r=mmadhjē-°mbu*.

⁵ Read *paṭta-bamḍha*.

Third Plate, First Side

- 67 m-ēva pupōsha yaḥ | **Jayasim̄has**-tṛiṇaṁ chakrē sarvasvaṁ svayam=ēva saḥ ||51 Uddam-
dō dadatāṁ paṭuḥ pravadatām=u-
- 68 jjāgarō jānatā[m̄] bhāvī śrī-**Jayasim̄ha** ity-avanipō dharmm-aika-va(ba)ddha-vrataḥ |
dauhitrō tra kulē vipaśchi-
- 69 d uchutaḥ pautrō=tra pātraṁ śrīvō(yō) matv=ēttham̄ khalu Śambhur=iṁdum=analaṁ
prīty-ōttamāṁgē dadhau ||52 Paulastya-mastaka-bhrasyad-asra-vi-
- 70 stā jaṭ-āṭavi¹ | karpūra-pūraṇair-yēna Purārēḥ surabhiḥ kṛitā || 53 **Vim̄dhy**-ādrēr=valayaṁ
vikaṁghya paritō dik-kūla-sarvvaṁkakhē(shē) sai-
- 71 nyē śrī-**Jayavarmmaṇaḥ** kshītipatēr=yasy=ālam-āskam̄dati | kām̄tābhiḥ khalu
Dākshinātya-nṛipatēḥ kōpād Agastyam̄ prati kshī-
- 72 p̄tāḥ prakshita-kām̄diśika-patibhiḥ krūrāḥ kaṭāksha-chchhaṭāḥ || 54 Su(Śu)bhr-ābhraṁ-
liha-hēma-kumbha-śirasō dē[v-ā*]layān=kārayan-viprē-
- 73 bhṛyō vitaran purāṇi kanakam̄ dhēnūḥ su(śu)bhāḥ kōṭīśaḥ | ārām̄n=iha rōpayan-sara-
sayam̄(yan)n uchchais-taḍāg-ōttamāḥ kshōṇī-maṁḍala-
- 74 m=ujva(jjva)lam̄ sthira-matir=yō-dy-āpi na śrāmyati ||55 Ittham̄ p̄ithvīm=avaty=asmin=
Ja(ñ-Ja)yavarmmaṇi bhūpatau [|*] vyāpārārna(n=a)pa(pi) mudrād[i]n=paripa[m̄]-
- 75 thayati² svayam̄(yam) ||56 **Chāhamāna**-kulē Rāṭō rāuttāḥ kramatō=bhavat | chaṁḍa-
dōr-ddam̄ḍayōr=yasya jaya-śrīḥ sthīratām-agāt || 57
- 76 Palhaṇadēvas-tasmād=a[bha]vad=bhujā-dam̄ḍa-maṁḍalī-chaṁḍaḥ | yaḥ svām̄ini jaya-
śrīyam=ātmani yaśa ēva ch-ādbhatta ||58 Salasha(kha)ṇasim̄-
- 77 has tasmāt=tanayō naya-bhūr-abhūt=subhujāḥ | **Arjjunadēvasy**-ājishu yasō(śō)-rjjanē
sa khalu saha-kṛitvā ||59 Jitvā **Sim̄haṇadēva**-du-
- 78 rddhara-mahāsainyam̄ chamū-nāyakam̄ mādhyāt=Śāgaya-rāṇakam̄ svayam=ih-ādhaḥ pāta-
yitvā hayāt | tasmāt=paṭṭamayāni sapta samarē
- 79 yaś=chāmarāny-agrahīn=mūrdhānau paridhūnayan=rasa-vasā(śā)t=**Sim̄h-Ārjjuna**-ksham̄-
bhujōḥ || 60 Tasmād-**Anayasim̄hō**=[bhū]t=kalāvān=iva
- 80 vāridhēḥ | ya ēkaḥ Kalpa-vṛiksh-ādi-madhyē gaṇanay=ānvitaḥ ||61 Dēvapālapurē yēna
prāsādē kārītē Śivaḥ | śrām̄taḥ [kum̄]-
- 81 ḍa-jala-vyājāt=siddha-sim̄dhum̄ dadhau puraḥ ||62 Śākapurai(rē)=bhraṁliha-sisharam̄³
sura-sadanam=Am̄vi(bi)k-ādhighatam̄(tam) | yō=[chī]karad=iva dā[tum̄]
- 82 visrām̄(śrām̄)tiṁ khē dvijasya sam̄pra(bhṛa)mataḥ ||63⁴ Ōṁkāra-prāsādāṁ समयā nira-
māpayattarām̄ tuṁgam̄(gam) | Jam̄vū(bū)kēsvara-nām̄naḥ Sam̄(Śam̄)bhōr=yaḥ sadana-
- 83 m=anupam=iti⁵ ||64 Yat-kārītē sarasi **Maṁḍapa-durga**-madhyē Kum̄bhōdbhavaḥ prati-
nisam̄(śam̄) prativim̄vya⁶mānaḥ | jyē(jyō)tirmmayō lavaṇa-vā-

¹ For Rāvaṇa offering his heads to Śiva, cf. *Rāmāyana*, N.S. Press, Āraṇya-kāṇḍa, Canto XXXII, verse 18.

² Cf. Passages like *śrīśrīkaran-ādi-samasta-mudrā-ryāpārān paripanthayati* used in medieval documents (cf. *Lēkhapādhati*, pp. 2, 5, 17, 34, 35c.) with reference to a high administrative officer (often a viceroy) under the king. The word *paripanthayati* in such cases means the same thing as *samvyavaharati* in other inscriptions (cf. *Select Inscriptions*, pp. 284, text line 6; 286, text line 5; 324, text line 2; 328, text line 4; etc.), although this meaning of the verb is not found in the lexicons. In the present case the administrative function in question seems to have been carried out by the king himself.

³ Read *śkharam̄*.

⁴ The stanza becomes metrically satisfactory if we read *Śākapur-ākhyē* at the beginning.

⁵ Read *°pamam-iti*.

⁶ Read *°bim̄bva°*.

- 84 ridhi-vāri-pāna-duḥsvāda-duḥkham=iva mārṣṭi piva(ba)nn=apō=ntaḥ ||65 Prākārēṇa
pratōlyā śhaḍ-adhika-dasa(śa)bhir=maṁdiraiḥ sva-
- 85 rṇṇa-kuṁbhair=uttuṁgair=bhūri-kakshair=guru-sura-sadanēn=āṁvu(bu)-kuṁḍēna yuktān-
(ktām) | yō durgē Maṁḍapa-ākhē(khyē) vyatarad=iha purīm Vrā(Brā)hmaṇē-
- 86 bhyō nṛip-ājñām lavdhvā(bdhvā) Māndhātri-durgē=py=anupama-rachanaṁ tadvad=eṅva
vyadhatta || 66 sa ēsha pūrvv-ōkta-rāj-āvali-virājamānēna bha-
- 87 kṛy-ādibhiḥ prasāditēna śrīmaj-**Jayavarmmaṇā Dhār-ādhipēn**=ānujñātaḥ Sa(Sā)dhanikō
=**nayasimhadēvō** dharmm-ādhat¹-saṁva(ba)ddha-vu(bu)-
- 88 ddhir=vijayī **Varddhanāpura**-pratijāgaraṇakē Kuṁbhadaūda-grāmē tathā tatr=aiva
Vālauda-grāmē tathā **Saptāsīti**-prati-
- 89 jāgaraṇakē Vaghāḍi-grāmē tathā **Nāgadaha**-pratijāgaraṇakē Nāṭiyā-grāmē samasta-
rājapurushān=Vrā(n=Brā)-

Third Plate, Second Side

- 90 hmaṇ-ōttarān=pratinivāsi-paṭṭakila-janapad-ādīmś=cha vō(bō)dhayaty=astu vaḥ samvi-
ditam yathā | **Maṁḍapa**-durg-āvasthitai-
- 91 r=asmābhir=**ēkatrimśad-adhika-trayōdaśa-śata-samkhy-ānvitē** Pramāthi-nāmni
samvatsarē Bhādrapadē māsi śukla-pakshē
- 92 **saptamyām tithau Śukra-dinē Maitrē² nakshatrē** snātvā bhagavanītam Pārvvatīpatiṁ
samabhyarehya saṁsārasy=āsāratām dṛiṣṭvā tathā
- 93 hi [*] Vāt-ābhra-vibhramam=idam vasudh-ādhipatyam=āpāta-mātra-madhurō viśhay-
ōpabhōgaḥ | prāṇās=trīn-āgra-jala-vimdu-samā narāṇām
- 94 dharmmaḥ sakhā param=ahō para-lōka-yānē [|| 67*] iti sarvvaṁ vimṛi[ś]y=ādīṣṭa-phalam=
aṅgīkṛitya cha sva-putraiḥ Kamalasiṁha-Dhārasīṁha-Jaitra-
- 95 siṁha-Padmasīṁha(hā) ity=ētaiḥ sahitai[h*] nānā-gōtrēbhyō nānā-nāmabhyō **Māndhātri**-
Vra=(Bra)hmapurī-vāstavyēbhyō Vrā(Brā)hmaṇēbhyāḥ ya-
- 96 thā Ṭakāri-sthāna-vinirgatāya Gautama-sagōtrāya Āṅgiras-Auvathya-[Gau]tam-ēti-tri-
pravarāya³ Ṛigvēda-śākh-ādhyā-
- 97 yinē Cha⁴-Kamalādharaśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Avasathi-Vidyādharaśarmmaṇaḥ putrāya
Dī⁵-Padmanābhaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya
- 98 padam=ēkam || 1 Ṭakāri-sthāna-vinirgatāya Gautama-sagōtrāya-Āṅgiras-Auvathya-Gautam-
ēti-tri-pravarāya Ṛigvēda-
- 99 śākh-ādhyāyinē Cha⁶-Kamalādharaśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Ava⁶-Vidyādharaśarmmaṇaḥ
putrāya Cha⁶-Mādhavaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇā-
- 100 ya padom=ēkam || 1 Ṭakāri-sthāna-vinirgatāya Bhāradvāja-sagōtrāya Āṅgirasa-Vā(Bā)-
rhaspatya-Bhāradvāj-ēti-tri-prava-

¹ The intended reading may be *dharm-ārtha*.

² The popular name of the constellation is *Anurādhā*.

³ According to many authorities, the *pravara*s of the Gautama *gōtra* are Āṅgirasa, Ayāsyā and Gautama, while those of the Utathya or Uchathya *gōtra* are Āṅgirasa, Utathya or Uchathya and Gautama.

⁴ This is a contraction of *Chaturvēdin*.

⁵ This is a contraction of *Dīkshita*.

⁶ This is a contraction of *Avasathin*.

- 101 rāya Ṛigvēda-śākhā-pravarddhamānāya Mīśra-Dharmadharaśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Pañcha-pīthi¹-Mīśra²-Uddharaṇaśarmmaṇaḥ putrāya Pañ³
- 102 Śrīkaṁṭhaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=ēkam || 1 Lasha(kha)ṇapura-vinirgatāya Kāśyapa-sagōtrāya Kāśyap-Āvatsāra-Naidhru-
- 103 v-ēti-tri-pravarāya Cha⁴-Bhō(Bhū)patiśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Pañ⁵-Vidyāpatiśarmmaṇaḥ putrāya Ṛigvēda-śākhā-pravarddhamānāya Dvi⁴-
- 104 Gōvardhanaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=ēkam || 1 Tōlāpauha-sthāna-vinirgatāya Chamdrātrēya-sagōtrāya Ātrēya-Gāvi-
- 105 shṭhira-Pūrvvātith-ēti-tri-pravarāya Dī⁶-Śrīvatsaśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Dī⁶-Dēvaśarmmaśarmmaṇaḥ putrāya Mādhyamīna-śā-
- 106 kh-ādhyāyinē Dī⁶-Vāmanaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=ēkam || 1 Ṭakārī-sthāna-vinirgatāya Vāśishṭha-sagōtrā-
- 107 ya Vāśishṭha-Śāktrya-Pārāsary-ēti-tri-pravarāya Va(Ba)labhadraśarmmaṇaḥ p[au]trāya Sādharmaśarmmaṇaḥ putrāya Mādhyamī-
- 108 na-śākh-ādhyāyinē Avasthi⁵-Anantaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=ēkam || 1 Ṭakārī-sthāna-vinirgatāya [Bh]āra-
- 109 dvāja-sagōtrāya Āngirasa-Vā(Bā)ṛhaspatya-Bhāradvāj-ēti-tri-pravarāya Śukla-Pradyumnaśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Dvi⁶-Sō-
- 110 lūśarmmaṇaḥ putrāya Mādhyamīna-śākh-ādhyāyinē Dvi⁶-Hariśarmmaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=ēkam || 1
- 111 Ṭēṇī-sthāna-vinirgatāya Kāśyapa-sagōtrāya Kāśyap-Āvatsāra-Naidhruv-ēti-tri-pravarāya Upā⁶-⁶
- 112 Dēvaśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Upā⁶-Vaijūśarmmaṇaḥ putrāya Mādhyamīna-śākh-ādhyāyinō Dvi⁶-[Ma]-

Fourth Plate, First Side

- 113 [hā]dēvaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=ēkam || 1 Ṭakārī-sthāna-vinirgatāya Kātyāyana-sagōtrāya Vi[śvā]-
- 114 [mi]tra-Kātya-Kīl⁷-ēti-tri-pravarā[ya] Pā⁸-Kūlhanaśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Ava⁶-Āladēvaśarmmaṇaḥ putrāya
- 115 Mādhyamīna-śākh-ādhyāyinē Dvi⁶-Har[i]dēvaśarmmaṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam ēkam || 1 Ṭakārī-sthāna-vinirgatāya [Bh]āradvāja-
- 116 sagōtrāya Āngirasa-Vā(Bā)[r]haspatya-Bhāradvāj-ēti-tri-pravarāya Dvi⁶-Gajādharmaśarmmaṇaḥ pautrāya Ava⁶-Vi[nikū]dēvaśarmmaṇaḥ

¹ The intended word seems to be *pāthi*.

² *Sandhi* has not been observed here.

³ This is a contraction of *Pañcha-pī(pā)thin* or more probably *Pañdita*.

⁴ This is a contraction of *Drivēdin*.

⁵ Sanskrit *Arasathin*. *Sandhi* has not been observed here.

⁶ This may be a contraction of *Upāsana* or more probably *Upādhyāya*.

⁷ The correct form of the name is *Atkila* according to many authorities.

⁸ This may be a contraction of *Pāthin*.

iii, b

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Scale : Two-fifths

- 117 putrāya Mādhyam̄dina-sākh-ādhyāyinē Dvi°-Anam̄tasarm̄maṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam
=ēkam || 1 Ṭakār[i]-sthāna-vinirgatāya Ā-
- 118 trēya-sagōtrāya Ātrēya-G[ā]viṣṭhira-Pūrvvātith-ēti-tri-pravarāya Pā°-K[ri]shṇasarm̄maṇaḥ
pautrāya Pā°-Atrisarm̄maṇaḥ putrā-
- 119 ya Mādhyam̄dina-sākh-ādhyāyinē Pā°-Y[ō]gēsvaraśarm̄maṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=
ēkam || 1 Ṭakārī-sthāna-vinirgatāya Vaśi-
- 120 shṭha-sagōtrāya Vāśiṣṭh-Ābharadvasv-Im̄drapramad-ēti-tri-pravarāya Tri°-Samuddharaṇa-
śarm̄maṇaḥ pautrāya Tri°-Dāmōdaraśarm̄maṇaḥ pu-
- 121 trāya Kauthuma-sākh-ādhyāyinē Tri°-Nārāyaṇaśarm̄maṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=ēkam
|| 1 Ṭakārī-sthāna-vinirgatāya Sāva-
- 122 rṇṇi-sagōtrāya Bhārgava-(Chyavana-Āpnavāna-Aurvva°-Yā(Jā)madagny-ēti-paiucha-prava-
rāya° Cha°-Vāsudēvaśarm̄maṇaḥ] pautrāya Cha°-Lakshmī-
- 123 dha[ra]śarm̄maṇaḥ putrāya Kauthuma-sākh-ādhyāyinē Tri°-Purushūśarm̄maṇē Vrā(Brā)-
[hma]ṇāya pa[da]m=ēkam || 1 Ṭeṇī-sthāna-vinirgatā-
- 124 ya Śāmdilya-sagōtrāya Śāmdily-Āśi(si)ta-Daival-ēti-tri-pravarāya Tri°-Viśvēsvaraśarm̄maṇaḥ
pautrāya Tri°-Mahēsvarasarm̄ma[ṇaḥ]
- 125 [pu]trāya Kauthuma-sākh-ādhyāyinē Tri°-Vāūm̄śarm̄maṇē Vrā(Brā)hmaṇāya padam=ēkam
|| 1 Vatsa-sagōtrāya Bhārgava-Chyavana-Āpna-
- 126 vāna-Aurvva°-Jāmadagnē(gny-ē)ti-pa[m̄]cha-pravarāya Chāhamāna-ku[l]lō pravarddhamānāya
Sā°-Palhaṇadēvavarm̄maṇaḥ pautrāya Sā°-Sala-
- 127 sha(kha)ṇasīha°varm̄maṇaḥ putrāya Śādhanika°-Anayasim̄havarm̄maṇaḥ Kshatriyāya pada-
dvayam || 2 iti shōḍasa(śa)-Vrā(Brā)hmaṇēbhyaḥ
- 128 Ku[m̄]bhadaudā(da)-Vālaudā(da)-Vaghāḍī-Nāṭiyā iti grāma-chatusṭayam samagram̄ chatush-
kam-kaṭa-visu(śu)ddham̄ sa-vṛiksha-māl-ākulam̄ ta-
- 129 t-sam̄va(ba)ddha-griha-grihasthāna-khala-khalasthānam̄ khalu tala-bhēdyā-gōvāṭikā-sāka-
musṭi-tailapalikā-kumbhapūrak-ātkā(kā)-
- 130 ś-ōtpatti-pātāla-nidhi-nikshōpa-[d]vāyata[n]-ōdyāna-taḍāga-vāpī-kūp-āḍi-sahitam̄ sa-hi-
raṇya-bhāga-bhōga[m̄*] s-ō-
- 131 parikara[m̄*] dam̄ḍ-ādi-[sar]v-ādāya-sahitam̄ puṇya-yaśō-bhivṛiddhayē chandr-ārka-ārṇava-
kshiti-sama-kālam̄ yāvat parayā bhaktyā dē-
- 132 va-Vrā(Brā)hmaṇa-bhukti-varjjam̄ śāsanēn=ōdaka-pūrvvam̄ dattam̄ tan=matvā tan-nivāsi-
patṭakila-janapadair=yathā-dīyamāna-bhāga-bhō-
- 133 ga-kara-hiraṇy-ādikam=ājñā-vidhēyair=bhūtvā sarvvam=ētēbhya[ō] Vrā(Brā)hmaṇēbhya[h*]
sam[u]panētavyam̄ sāmānyam̄ ch=aitad-dha[r]mma-[pha*]lam̄ vudhvā°
- 134 aśmat-svāmi-vam̄sa(śa)[air]=bhāvibhir=bhokṭribhir=asmad-datta dharm̄mā(rmma)-dāyō=
numam̄tavyaḥ pālānīyaś=cha | uktam̄ cha || Va(Ba)hubhir=vasudhā bhū-

¹ This is a contraction of *Trivēdin*.

² Read *Chyavan-Āpna* (or *pnu*) *rad-Aurvva*.

³ The *pravara*s of the *Sāvarni gōtra* are *Bhārgava*, *Vaṭahavya* and *Sāvēdasa* according to many authorities.

⁴ This is a contraction of *Sādhanika*.

⁵ The Sanskrit form of the name is *Sallakṣhaṇasim̄ha*°.

⁶ *Sandhi* has not been observed here.

⁷ Read *buddhvā*.

135 ktā rājabhi[ḥ*] Sagar-ādibhiḥ | yasya yasya yadā bhūmis=tasya tasya tadā phalam(lam)
 || [68*] Sva-dattām para-dattām vā yō hareta vasum̄dharām(rām |)

Fourth Plate, Second Side

- 136 sa viśṭhāyām kṣimir=bhūtvā pitṛibhiḥ saha majjati [|| 69*] Sarvvān-ēvaṁ bhāvinō bhūmi-
 pālān=bhūyō bhūyō yāchatē Rāmabhadraḥ |
- 137 sāmānyō=yam dharmma-sētur=nṛipāṇām kāl[ē] kālē pālānīyō bhavadbhiḥ || [70*] Iti kamala-
 dal-ānvu(bu)-vin̄du-lōlām śriyam=a-
- 138 nuchi[m̄]tya manushya-jīvitam̄ cha | sakalam=idam=udāhṛitam̄ cha vu(bud)dhvā na hi purush-
 aiḥ para-kirttayō vilōpyā[ḥ || 71*] iti ||
- 139 Śrikam̄thēna niyuktēna sabhāya[m̄](yān) **Jayavarmmaṇā** | chakrē kula-kram-āyātū(ta)-
 traividyatvēna śāsanam̄(nam) || [72*] utkīrṇam̄ cha ru(rū)pa-
- 140 kāra-Kānhākē¹na ||

¹ Originally *kō* was engraved.

MANDHATA PLATES OF PARAMARA JAYASIMHA-JAYAVARMAN, V. S. 1331

iv. b

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ॐ नमो भगवते वासुदेवाय ॥ इति मन्दाताप्लेखे ॥
 ॐ नमो भगवते वासुदेवाय ॥ इति मन्दाताप्लेखे ॥
 ॐ नमो भगवते वासुदेवाय ॥ इति मन्दाताप्लेखे ॥
 ॐ नमो भगवते वासुदेवाय ॥ इति मन्दाताप्लेखे ॥

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Scale : Two-fifths

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